

The Current Situation, Problems and Improvement Countermeasures of Industrial Access System in Grand Canal Business District, Beijing City Sub-Center

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ABSTRACT

Central business district (CBD) is an area where major business activities are carried out in a country or a big city. It is a symbol and symbol of a city's business card and economic modernization. The industrial access, business operation and business management of CBD need good legal environment to support and guarantee. With the in-depth implementation of the coordinated development strategy of Beijing, Tianjin and Hebei, the status of Beijing City Sub-center in the construction of the capital's economy, politics, culture and Beijing Tianjin Hebei business service area has been further improved. The construction of canal business district is an important part of the plan and construction of Beijing Sub-center. Located at the intersection of the five rivers, the canal business district is one of the main areas and demonstration areas for the construction of Beijing's Sub-center. At present, the infrastructure of canal business district, the Sub-center of Beijing City, has been gradually put into use, and some industrial projects are entering the park and being fully constructed. In order to promote the implementation of the planning and function optimization of the canal business district, it is very important to establish the legal system and policy system of the entry threshold, system design, policy incentive, exit mechanism and so on. At present, the relevant legal system of Beijing for the industrial access of business district needs to be improved; the construction of industrial access mechanism needs to be improved; the main body, form and mechanism of industrial access need to be optimized. Based on the new Beijing Sub-center canal business district in Tongzhou and the industrial access system needed for the development of new CBD, as well as its functional orientation and nature, this paper considers and studies, and puts forward the strategies for promoting the standardization of the industrial access system of Beijing Sub-center canal business district: strengthening the top-level system design of industrial access in the central business district at the national level; improving the industrial access system Specific legal policy system design; improve the implementation system of industrial project access in the canal business district; improve the judicial guarantee system of industrial access in the canal business district, the Sub-center of Beijing city; improve the market self-discipline and industry self-discipline mechanism of industrial access in the canal business district, better realize the CBD construction of the Beijing Sub-center canal, and provide for the sustainable, healthy and rapid development of the city's Sub-center economy Legal protection

KEYWORDS: *Beijing City Sub-center; Canal business district; Industry access; System construction*

I. INRODUCTION

In September 2017, the State Council officially approved the plan of Beijing master plan 2016-2035. Within the Sub-center area of Beijing, the canal business district is an important part. We will comprehensively implement the latest concepts and the highest standards proposed by the central government, the Beijing Municipal Party committee and the high government, take the intersection of five rivers, namely the starting point of the Beijing Hangzhou Universiade in Hebei, take high-end business enterprises as the main body, take headquarters economy as the form, and focus on high-end high-tech industries such as financial innovation, Internet industry and high-end services, to build

a new super CBD with water city integration and blue-green interconnection, and work with the state In response, trade CBD forms two major economic growth points along the east of Chang'an Street. In December 2018, Beijing Sub-center regulatory detailed planning (block level) (2016-2035) was released and implemented, which provides planning guidance for industrial planning, structural adjustment and industrial access of Beijing Sub-center, as well as planning basis and guidance for the construction of canal business district. The purpose of this paper is to better realize the construction of CBD Industrial Park and provide legal guarantee for the rapid development of Beijing's Sub-center

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economy by analyzing the theoretical basis and practical development of the industrial access system of Beijing's Sub-center canal business district.

A. Research purpose

In September, 2016, the State Council officially approved the plan of Beijing master plan for 2016-2035 [2]. Within the Sub-center area of Beijing, the canal business district is an important part. We will comprehensively implement the latest concepts and the highest standards proposed by the central government, the Beijing Municipal Party committee and the high government, take the intersection of five rivers, namely the starting point of the Beijing Hangzhou Universiade in Hebei, take high-end business enterprises as the main body, take headquarters economy as the form, and focus on high-end high-tech industries such as financial innovation, Internet industry and high-end services, to build a new super CBD with water city integration and blue-green interconnection, and work with the state. In December 2018, Beijing Sub-center regulatory detailed planning (block level) (2016-2035) was released and implemented, which provides planning guidance for industrial planning, structural adjustment and industrial access of Beijing Sub-center, as well as planning basis and guidance for the construction of canal business district. The purpose of this paper is to better realize the construction of CBD Industrial Park and provide legal guarantee for the rapid development of Beijing Sub-center economy by analyzing the theoretical basis and practical development of the industrial access system of Beijing Sub-center canal business district.

B. Research significance

1. Theoretical significance

The construction of Beijing Sub-center has been on the right track. With the continuous promotion of planning and the introduction of new policies, the development of Business Industrial Park in the Grand Canal area will gradually face various problems. The improvement of a legal mechanism is often the result of the coordination of multiple interest mechanisms. This paper will study the industrial access system and horizontal package of Beijing Sub-center canal business district Including the coordinated management of various aspects of enterprises such as finance, high-end business services, culture and Tourism Internet industry, there are vertical links of legislation, law enforcement, justice, the construction structure of the central business district, the construction of the internal standard and innovation mechanism of enterprises, etc. Therefore, it is particularly important to explore the relevant policy research in theory, and establish the industrial access system of Beijing Sub-center canal business district. This topic actively expands the research field of the industrial project access theory of the canal business district, the Sub-center of the city.

(1) The subject chooses the access mechanism of industrial projects in Beijing Sub-center canal business district which has not been paid enough attention by the academic community. The application of multi-disciplinary concepts such as law, industrial economics and public management to carry out special research, combined with the research results of the Grand Canal cultural belt and economic belt theory, will help theoretical researchers and practitioners to fully understand and more accurately grasp the access

theory and practice mode of industrial projects in Yunhe business district, Beijing Sub-center, and expand the existing access laws and policies of business district Theoretical research field.

(2) This project explores and improves the industrial access regulation mechanism and mode of Beijing Sub-center canal business district. Guided by the new development concept of "innovation, coordination, green, opening and sharing", the research results can complement, enrich, develop and improve the academic system of the access mechanism of the urban Sub-center business district, and promote the construction of relevant academic research and disciplines. Adhere to the concept and principle of social standard, balanced coordination and comprehensive system adjustment, and construct the legal and policy mechanism, adjustment mode and implementation path for the access of urban Sub-center business district.

2. Practical significance

This research is to strengthen the construction of Beijing Sub-center. In the construction of canal business district, the Sub-center of Beijing, we should optimize the layout and spatial structure of the city, focus on areas, strive to match the strategic positioning of the capital city with high-tech development mode, coordinate the economic development mode, and adapt to the population, resources and environment. The construction of the canal business district in the vice heart of Beijing city needs to be based on the new overall planning of Beijing city. The canal business district will be built into a comprehensive functional area, focusing on financial innovation, Internet industry and high-end services. It is an important carrier to realize the transfer of commercial functions of the central city. Located at the intersection of the five rivers, the canal business district is the main area and demonstration area for the construction of the city's Sub-center. At present, the infrastructure of the business district has been gradually put into use, and some industrial projects are under comprehensive construction. How to construct the access threshold, policy incentive and exit mechanism of industrial projects in Beijing Sub-center canal business district is very important. One of the key links in the construction of the canal business district is to improve the access mechanism of industrial projects in the canal Business District of Beijing Sub-center.

(1) This project is helpful to solve the practical problems in the access mechanism construction of canal business district, the Sub-center of Beijing. The project research is an objective need to implement the spirit of the 19th National Congress of the Communist Party of China, the outline of coordinated development of Beijing, Tianjin and Hebei, the strategic task of the 13th five year plan of the state, the 13th five year plan of Beijing, and the construction plan of Beijing's urban Sub-center. Chen Jining, mayor of Beijing Municipal People's government, pointed out that the functional orientation of the canal business district should be further clarified; according to the new Beijing urban master plan, the canal business district will be built into a comprehensive functional area focusing on financial innovation, Internet industry and high-end service, which is an important carrier to carry the business function of the central city. In view of the new urban master plan, this area will be built into a comprehensive functional area focusing on financial innovation, Internet industry and high-end services, which is

an important carrier to carry out the business function of the central urban area; the research conclusion of this subject will provide theoretical basis and model construction for promoting the improvement of the legal and policy mechanism and mode of industrial project access of Beijing Sub-center canal business area Discussion.

(2) This topic is helpful to solve the important concept and practical problems in the construction of the access mechanism of the industrial projects in the canal business district, the Sub-center of Beijing. Cai Qi, Secretary of the Beijing Municipal Party committee, proposed to check the projects that want to enter the vice center, and raise the entry threshold according to the city's catalogue of prohibitions and restrictions. Put forward clear requirements for the functional orientation of the canal business district, focus on the cultivation and introduction of headquarters and finance, and the industrial cultivation should move towards high-end and high-end. This project is an urgent need to strengthen the construction and development of Sub-center business district. As the core of Beijing's new CBD space, the source island of five water parallel flow has become the link and leisure node of the business district, and constructed a people-oriented business district space system. Under the background of canal culture construction, based on the new development concept, the research results of this subject will help to improve the legal and policy guarantee level of the construction of Beijing Sub-center canal business district; deepen the application research of industrial project access theory of urban Sub-center canal business district, provide intellectual support and theoretical support, and solve the outstanding problems of industrial project access of urban Sub-center canal business district To promote the sustainable, healthy and coordinated development of the construction of the sub Central Business District of the city.

C. Research status at home and abroad

1. Domestic research status

For this topic, most scholars study the construction of the Sub-center and the planning of the central business district, few scholars put forward relevant opinions directly for this topic. Wang Chengrong put forward in "thinking about the development of new CBD in Tongzhou District, the Sub-center of Beijing city" [1], Tongzhou District shoulders the important responsibility of developing the new CBD function in Beijing, "Beijing Tianjin Hebei integration" situation, Beijing's business function is more prominent, Tongzhou, as an important role in Beijing Tianjin Hebei, is the best choice for Beijing to develop new CBD in the future. At the same time, the paper puts forward that the constraints of Tongzhou District to develop Beijing's new CBD are the weak industrial foundation and the constraints of natural environment and water resources, so as to analyze the positioning and characteristics of Tongzhou District to build Beijing's new CBD. Yuan Songhua put forward in "Beijing Urban Sub-center construction promotes Beijing, Tianjin and Hebei to become the third pole of China's economy" [2], the construction of Beijing Urban Sub-center rises to a national strategy, which is not only the need to adjust Beijing's spatial pattern, manage big city diseases, expand new development space, but also the need to promote the coordinated development of Beijing, Tianjin and Hebei, and explore the optimized development mode of densely populated areas. Zheng Ruifang put forward in the international comparison

and Enlightenment of Beijing's construction of Tongzhou City Sub-center [3], that the construction of Tongzhou City Sub-center is a national strategy, and also a key work of Beijing during the 13th Five Year Plan period. The construction of Tongzhou City Sub-center puts forward higher requirements for the comprehensive carrying capacity of Tongzhou District, which is convenient transportation system, good ecological environment, reasonable population and employment distribution. It is suggested that we should pay attention to the improvement of comprehensive carrying capacity in the near future, industrial development in the medium term, and policy stability and sustainability in the long term.

2. Research status abroad

In the morden city central business district evolution simulation [4], Liu Peng Zhu, Shuming Jiang, Shijie Xu and Jinfeng Miao proposed that the layout mode of CBD structure focus often reflects the centripetal force of key enterprises' agglomeration development in spatial layout, which reflects the changes of industrialization process, economic scale and transportation technology. Foreign experiments mainly simulate the changes of urban spatial layout brought by industrial spatial layout to enterprises. The evolution process of CBD diffusion is the most common way, which is stable expansion, small and irregular boundary changes, and the overall changes have certain limitations, which makes the buildings around CBD gradually replaced by new commercial buildings, thus forming some continuous zones. This kind of high-end industry is essentially a kind of behavior of continuous renewal of the original city, but on the whole, CBD diffusion is steady The performance of the situation, and continue to spread. Under the guidance of the government and the promotion of the society, CBD expands rapidly. In the explosive expansion, the CBD boundary will advance in a specific direction and develop towards a thorough non-commercial area, instead of closing CBD in the same area. Although the continuous time is very short, the boundary of the promotion depth is very large, which promotes the prosperity of the whole region. In the following part, I will introduce the current situation and development of the legal system and system of CBD in the United States, Japan, Germany, Singapore and other countries according to the actual situation of each country, so as to serve as a reference for the improvement of China's legal system.

D. Definition of relevant concepts

1. Central business district

Central business district (CBD for short) refers to the area mainly engaged in commercial activities in a country or city. The concept was first developed in the United States in the 20th century and was defined as "a place where business concentration converges". In the next fifty or sixty years, the manufacturing industry of developed countries began to go out. At the same time, business gathered in the central area of the city, and constantly planned to build a modern business center with certain scale and characteristics.

The central business district is located in the central area of the city, marking the modernization of the city. As the core of the city, and even the center of national economic development, it highly concentrates the economic, scientific and technological and cultural resources of the city, with various functions such as finance, trade, service, exhibition and consultation; high-quality business office, hotel,

apartment and other facilities are gathered here, and first-class commercial buildings, large shopping centers, cultural and entertainment facilities are all available; with perfect transportation Communication and communication conditions, multiple subway and public transportation lines can be reached, and the communication between citizens from various regions to the central business district is very convenient; there are many companies, financial institutions and enterprise groups competing to hold business activities here, and the central business district is very prominent.

2. Canal business district, Beijing City Sub-center

Beijing City Sub-center canal business district is located in the intersection of Tonghui River, North Canal, Wenyu River, Xiaozhong River and Yunchao River in Tongzhou new city. The planning area is expanded from 160000 square kilometers to 480000 square kilometers. Relying on the profound cultural heritage and superior traffic conditions of the ancient canal, a new Central business district is established in Beijing, integrating administrative office, business services and culture Tourism, high-end business and housing are integrated. As a demonstration area for the construction and development of new towns, this area has taken the opportunity of innovation and development, guided by the overall urban planning, built a comprehensive functional area focusing on finance, Internet and high-end services, alleviated the business function, improved the consumption level, supplemented international projects and gathered cultural industries in the central area of Beijing. It is the development of Beijing to build a world-class city with Chinese characteristics Sex area. The canal business district will actively introduce headquarters projects such as multinational companies, well-known enterprises and high-end private enterprises, reflecting the high-end business functions characterized by headquarters. The central area of Beijing Sub-center canal business district adopts top-level professional planning and design, which embodies the core concepts of green health, low-carbon environmental protection and comprehensive utilization of underground space. In the design of ground traffic, green traffic network is established to meet the needs of pedestrians to the greatest extent; in the design of buildings, green building materials, energy-saving design and other scientific and technological achievements are used; in the Municipal Administration In terms of management, we should actively use water resources recycling, rainwater recycling, garbage vacuum pipeline collection, etc.

3. Industry access system

There is no clear concept of industrial access system. In terms of its standards, the concept refers to the construction projects that do not meet the national industrial policies and industry access standards, and the land use shall not be approved. The main measures are to conscientiously implement the national industrial policies and strictly enforce the market access standards, so as to establish the industrial technology standards, market access standards and technological innovation system, and promote the circular economy. The industrial access of Beijing Sub-center canal business district refers to which industrial projects can be settled in the canal business district, which is usually adjusted by the "industrial access list" and "industrial negative list" policies of the business district. All market subjects must strictly follow the list access.

E. Research methods

1. Literature research

Through the method of literature retrieval, in China HowNet and foreign literature websites, according to the core issues of the selected topic, collect relevant literature, conduct induction and analysis, find out the relevant points in the literature that are related to their own arguments, or helpful for their own paper research, and deeply understand how the access mechanism of the business district industry in different regions is, and relevant departments can take What measures should be taken to standardize the standards for enterprises to enter the market and improve the quality of development.

2. Induction

On the basis of mastering relevant theoretical knowledge and material data, this paper analyzes and summarizes the current development of canal business district, the Sub-center of Beijing City, as well as the problems faced by the establishment of the three leading functions of administration, business service and culture and tourism, and sums up the relevant data on the settlement of financial and high-end service industries.

3. Comparative research method

This paper compares the development of Beijing Sub-center with that of domestic and foreign central business districts, compares and analyzes with domestic and foreign market access legislation and implementation cases, and focuses on the research of different national conditions and policy implementation premise. Combined with the national and Local Legislative Features and law enforcement experience, and drawing on the international advanced legislative and law enforcement experience, this paper studies the improvement path of the industrial access system and policy system of the canal business district.

II. Analysis of the current situation of the industrial access system construction of the canal business district, the Sub-center of Beijing.

This part focuses on the analysis of the operation status of the industrial project access construction of Beijing Urban Sub-center canal business district, which is the premise and basis for the optimization design of the industrial access system of the canal business district. It is necessary to make an empirical investigation and Analysis on the current situation of access mechanism construction and legal adjustment of industrial projects in Beijing Sub-center canal business district from the perspectives of access basis, access scope, access principle, access procedure, access review and access responsibility. At present, the access and construction of the canal business district urgently needs to find out the direction of financial development, strengthen the docking and cooperation with Xicheng Financial Street and Chaoyang CBD, undertake the industrial transfer, and actively promote the implementation of financial innovation business segment with its misplaced development; actively explore and expand the use of foreign investment to attract competitive private enterprises and transnational corporations Division of regional headquarters, cultivate a growth headquarters with innovative vitality.

A. Current situation of industrial access system construction of National Central Business District

In order to improve the grade and quality of the projects settled in the business district, ensure the order of the

projects settled in, guide the famous industries at home and abroad to settle in the real estate, give full play to the use value of the real estate, and establish a good image of the business district. According to the guidance catalogue of industrial structure adjustment and the catalogue of industrial prohibition and restriction, the industries settled in the business district are divided into three categories: (1) encourage the industries settled in: headquarters enterprises (enterprises complete registration and carry out main business activities according to law, have independent legal personality, pay taxes uniformly, and perform management and service functions for their subsidiaries and branches; business income of subordinate enterprises Accounting for no less than 30%, including no less than 15% of cultural and creative industries; banking, securities, insurance and other financial services; technology and information communication services, e-commerce, software design and development, and computer network services; business intermediary services, such as enterprise management services, legal services, tourism services, etc.; cultural and creative industries such as opera houses, art districts, films and television media Industry: high end fitness and entertainment, hotel catering, commodity trade, shopping and other leisure services. (2) restricted industries: enterprises engaged in real estate development projects; small-scale wholesale and retail, catering and hotel leisure services; various hospital clinics (including pet business, pet clinics and other related services); Automobile beauty, housekeeping services, home appliance recycling and other maintenance services; foot bath, beauty and hair care services supporting non Hotel and large-scale comprehensive entertainment projects Industry. (3) prohibited industries: production, processing and manufacturing industries other than research and development, sales, design, etc.; warehousing industries; industries with environmental pollution; operation of toxic, harmful, flammable and explosive and other dangerous goods and other wholesale and retail industries authorized by the non-government; non Hotel and large-scale comprehensive entertainment supporting chess and card rooms, game halls, etc.; industries expressly prohibited by laws and regulations.

First of all, in September 2017, the State Council officially approved the plan of Beijing master plan for 2016-2035. Within the Sub-center area of Beijing, the canal business district is an important part. Taking the planning of Hebei Xiong an New District, which is similar to the Beijing City Sub-center business district, as an example, the general secretary Xi Jinping's report at the nineteenth National Congress of the Communist Party of China pointed out: to ease the coordinated development of Beijing, Tianjin and Hebei with the function of "non Beijing capital" as a "nose" to promote the coordinated development of Beijing Tianjin Hebei, a high starting point plan and a high standard construction of Xiong an new area, so the Xiong an new area is built at the very beginning. It is confirmed that the primary task is to undertake the non capital function of Beijing: in terms of educational and teaching institutions, it mainly undertakes the establishment of branch schools, national scientific research institutes and research centers in the new area by famous universities; in terms of medical and health institutions, it mainly undertakes the establishment of branch schools in the new area by high-end medical institutions, so as to strengthen the communication and

cooperation with well-known medical experts and research centers at home and abroad; in the financial industry On the one hand, it focuses on the headquarters of banking, insurance, securities and other financial institutions and encourages enterprises to actively innovate; on the high-end service industry, it focuses on the advantageous enterprises such as network and information service consulting, creative design, as well as the headquarters of modern logistics, e-commerce and other popular enterprises today; on the other hand, it supports ZhongGuanCun Science and technology park to set up a sub Park in Xiong'an new area.

Secondly, in December 2018, the detailed regulatory planning of Beijing Sub-center (block level) (2016-2035) was released and implemented, which provides planning guidance for industrial planning, structural adjustment and industrial access of Beijing Sub-center, as well as planning basis and guidance for the construction of canal business district. Xiong'an new area has made clear the negative list and positive list of industry access. Among the key industries, the new generation of information technology industry and high-end modern service industry are the top priority: the new generation of information technology industry focuses on the construction of digital city, the development of communication network, Internet of things, big data, cloud computing, artificial intelligence, network information security and other information technology industries, and the creation of The new artificial intelligence platform strives to achieve the breakthrough of unmanned system intelligence technology, and supports the industrial development and platform application of unmanned system. The high-end modern service industry is in line with the international standards, integrating banking, insurance, securities and other objectives to develop the financial service industry; building a service chain around innovative technology, developing business incubation, intellectual property, scientific and technological consulting and other scientific and technological services; building an international business headquarters base, developing design, exhibition, e-commerce and other business services; enriching domestic culture and expanding international cultural exchanges In accordance with the general promotion trend of international commercial law, we will develop international arbitration, law firms and other legal services.

Finally, the national industrial and information related departments have organized and revised the catalogue of industrial transfer guidance, which aims to successfully complete the industrial transfer work under the guidance of the market and the assistance of the government, and at the same time, develop the industry with high quality, so as to promote the coordinated development of industrial structure among regions, continuously promote the stable development of modern industry and promote the system with high standards Manufacturing development. Compared with the 2012 version, it is more clear about the projects that need to be developed and industries that need to be undertaken in each region in the future, so that the development of emerging industries and the undertaking of industrial transfer in other regions can be carried out at the same time, highlighting the characteristics of each region, and developing different types of industries according to local conditions, so as to promote economic development.

B. Current situation of industrial access system construction of Beijing Sub-center Business District

The 13th five year plan for Beijing's national economic and social development points out that the plan must be made closely around the realization of the "two centenary goals" of the Communist Party of China, until 2020 to build a moderately prosperous society in an all-round way. Seize the major historical opportunities, meet the challenges, accelerate the pace to build the world's top livable capital, and open the door to the capital. The 13th five year plan of Beijing mainly guides and explains the next process, emphasizing that we should stand at a new historical starting point, adhere to the strategic positioning of the capital city, optimize and improve the core functions of the capital region and orderly disperse the non capital functions, accelerate the coordinated development of the region, strengthen the environmental protection, increase the green space, build a low-carbon and environmental protection living environment, and We will build Beijing's infrastructure with high quality and standards, speed up efforts to relieve the traffic pressure in the city's central area, keep abreast of the national development trend, strive to optimize the structure of scientific and technological innovation, protect and disseminate history and culture, and establish a complete social security system to make the city's atmosphere younger and more dynamic. We will comprehensively deepen reform and opening up, strengthen legal system construction, and ensure the construction of Winter Olympic venues and Winter Olympic Games Preparations for all matters before the meeting. On the whole, we should take the national policy as the benchmark, deal with different types of development problems such as politics, economy and culture in Beijing from various aspects, improve the quality of personnel, strictly enforce the industrial access, and strive to build a perfect and harmonious city.

1. Optimize the structure of foreign capital utilization

We will support the development of the headquarters of multinational companies in line with the positioning of Beijing as the capital, encourage the operation of other departments of the entity, such as research and development projects, financial settlement, international sales, capital investment, and support their participation in urban infrastructure construction. At the same time, foreign-funded enterprises are encouraged to carry out R & D and innovation in Beijing, apply for the establishment of scientific research workstations, encourage high-level R&D activities, participate in the construction of scientific research projects and innovation and entrepreneurship platforms in Beijing and even in the whole country. We will focus on science and technology and financial services, accelerate the pace of innovation, and improve the utilization of foreign capital in key functional areas such as Beijing's Sub-center, central business district and financial street.

2. Create a good business environment

We will strengthen the protection of intellectual property rights and establish a patent arbitration and dispute mediation mechanism. We will improve the enforcement mechanism for intellectual property rights, promote coordination between administrative and judicial protection, and crack down on violations of law. We will build a service center for intellectual property protection and a center for

reporting and complaining, and provide legal advice and support services for enterprises. We will strengthen cooperation among all departments, use Beijing public credit information service platform and Beijing enterprise credit information network to shift the focus of supervision and management from market access to innovative corporate governance, and encourage companies with good reputation.

C. Current situation of industrial access system construction of canal business district, Beijing City Sub-center

1. Strict access and management of industrial projects

In order to implement the 2016-2035 Beijing urban master plan and the implementation of the outline of Beijing Tianjin Hebei coordinated development plan, Beijing has organized the preparation of the Beijing Sub-center regulatory detailed planning (block level) (2016-2035), and orderly promoted the planning and construction of Tongzhou new city, the Sub-center of Beijing.. To strictly control the industrial projects that want to enter the canal business district, the Sub-center of Beijing, to add new contents on the basis of the original forbidden catalogue of Beijing, and to raise the industry threshold of entering the business district, it is urgent to formulate the measures for the administration of the industrial project access system of the canal business district. For the projects that have been sold or have not been sold, they should be based on the industry form and the business district environment at the time of entry In order to enhance the attraction of Tongzhou District to the financial industry, we should supervise and control the access system such as the guarantee standard and the contribution rate to the economy, and strengthen the management in an all-round way.

2. Orderly introduction of financial and headquarters projects

At present, the wealth management center is located in the canal business district, the Sub-center of Beijing. The canal business district covers an area of 17.5 square kilometers and is an important bearing area for high-end business. At present, infrastructure construction such as three-dimensional transportation and comprehensive pipe gallery has been basically completed, and 16 development projects in phase I have been fully launched. Bank of China, industrial and Commercial Bank of China, China Construction Bank, Agricultural Bank of China, Bank of communications and other major banks have settled down. A number of financial institutions, such as Beijing Financial Science and Technology International Industrial Park, have officially settled in. The trend of financial industry cluster development initially shows that the introduction of headquarters type enterprises is the key to encourage the development of financial industry, which is oriented to high-end business, cultural tourism, administrative office, cultural creativity, scientific and technological innovation And other fields to optimize the advanced, precise and cutting-edge industrial structure. Through consulting well-known companies at home and abroad to carry out international bidding work, it reflects the preliminary results of Tongzhou District's industrial planning. At present, projects such as Greenland Central Plaza, Xinguang University Center, and world overseas Chinese business center in the canal business district, the Sub-center of Beijing City, have been completed in succession, many commercial offices, apartments and other industries have signed contracts, and the construction

sales work is proceeding steadily. Tongzhou District also plans to introduce several multinational companies or large group companies, listed cultural and creative industries and institutions, focusing on the development of high-end creative innovation and animation design industries.

3. Set up a benchmark for investment promotion

Under the guidance of the District Committee and the district government, Xinhua Street will cooperate with the New Town Management Committee, cooperate with the property management committee, enterprises and social organizations, earnestly perform their duties, explore innovative working methods, give full play to the active role of all units in building construction and social governance system innovation, ensure the service management of the canal business district to achieve results, create features, and build a "joint construction" "Co governance, sharing" governance. In terms of investment promotion, we will further study the headquarters economy, wealth management, business tourism, culture and technology, cutting-edge chips, information software, intelligent manufacturing and other industrial clusters in the canal business district, the Sub-center of Beijing city. We will make clear the functional positioning and industrial layout, improve the introduction and landing standards with international standards, and introduce a number of industrial projects that meet the functional positioning of the Sub-center of Beijing city to Tongzhou for development. Show the connotation of industrial agglomeration in the business district. Among them, Universal Studios theme park is the leading role of the "cultural tourism" industry cluster. When it opens in a few years, it will drive a number of hotels, restaurants, entertainment and other related enterprises to settle in Tongzhou. According to the overall planning of industrial development along the Grand Canal in Beijing, one of the next key development targets is the cultural and creative industry, which integrates the surrounding scenery of the Grand Canal to build a viewing and leisure area and shape the canal cultural landscape. Strengthen the cooperation with Xicheng District Financial Street and Chaoyang District CBD, carry out industrial transfer, introduce private enterprises and regional headquarters of multinational companies, and realize the innovation industry integrating technology and finance.

III. Bottleneck constraints in the construction of industrial access system of Beijing Sub-center canal business district

A. The legal system of industrial access of business district in Beijing needs to be improved

First of all, the 13th five year plan of Beijing has the function of laws and regulations, which guides and standardizes the development of business industry. If the government considers that it is necessary to carry out legal restraint after considering the public interest needs a specific industry, it is necessary to take immediate measures against its operators, but it is not allowed to adopt discriminatory standards against operators. At the same time, we can also choose to control the market access of the industry before the start of industrial business activities. The premise of this approach is to protect a wide range of interests.

Secondly, Beijing Sub-center regulatory detailed planning (block level) is issued, which plays an important role in planning guidance. However, different types of licensing conditions are used to control market access. For example,

whether the government reviews the access depends on whether the conditions of the application industry are qualified, whether the license is issued formally, and the business ability of the parties concerned. For example, according to the current situation of the industry, it is decided whether to allow or add new operators. However, doing so has certain restrictions on competition, which no longer values the application. The ability of the industry depends on the government's measurement of the objective situation, which greatly reduces the predictability of market access behavior.

Finally, some industries are monopolized by some operators licensed by the government, and other operators are no longer allowed to participate. Franchising is a special preferential treatment given by the government to lower the threshold of access, which makes a certain industry obtain the right to enter. This is very different from market access. Market access recognizes that industrial operators have the right to engage in this business activity, which is based on free competition. As for the allocation of resources in dispute, they are quite different in legal nature, so the franchise rights should be limited.

B. The access mechanism of Beijing's Sub-center industry needs to be improved

Beijing's central industry access system and mechanism are not perfect, and there is no clear positive and negative list of industry access. Beijing Sub-center and Hebei xiong'an new area are two new areas for Beijing's development. Tongzhou new area should actively contrast and connect with the planning of xiong'an new area, and further clarify the functional orientation and development ideas of the city's Sub-center. First of all, in the process of relieving the non capital function of the central urban area, a plan list is made and a work plan is designed for each step to achieve a precise and precise undertaking and play the role of relieving driving the non capital function. Secondly, accelerate the development of new high-end industries, vigorously promote the reform of the investment approval system, optimize and improve the regional business environment, drive the high-quality development of the Sub-center, and truly build the core area of Beijing's service function. Then it is to shape the Sub-center green ecological livable characteristics, as a green corridor to build natural semi natural waterfront embankment, and build a harmonious and unified sustainable development city of human and nature. Finally, we should handle the connection between the planning of Beijing Sub-center canal business district and the overall planning of Tongzhou District, build the Sub-center into a new town with distinctive characteristics, and realize the integrated development of Tongzhou and the coordinated development of Beijing, Tianjin and Hebei.

C. The main body, form and mechanism of industrial access of canal business district, Beijing City Sub-center still need to be optimized.

1. The construction of the access mechanism for industrial projects in the canal business district, the Sub-center of Beijing, should fully implement the new development concept of innovation, coordination, green, opening and sharing

The new development concept and the basic requirements of the construction and reform of the city's Sub-center need to be implemented in the access concept framework and the

legal and policy guarantee mechanism of Beijing's Sub-center canal business district. Based on the positioning of the city's Sub-center, we should attach importance to the high-end service industry, make full use of the policy advantages of Beijing's service industry, further expand the opening up, comprehensively promote and upgrade, and further plan the function and layout of the canal business district. On the basis of rational planning of land use functions, the sustainable development of commercial structure, commercial services, public facilities and residential functions should be rational.

2. The construction of the legal guarantee mechanism for the access of industrial projects in the canal business district, the Sub-center of Beijing, should implement the concept of social standard, balanced coordination, source control and comprehensive system adjustment

The advanced concept of urban economic governance has an important guiding function for the construction of legal and policy guarantee mechanism of industrial project access in Beijing Sub-center canal business district. The advanced concept can guide the construction of laws, regulations and policy system of industrial project access in Beijing Sub-center canal business district. To study and formulate the draft measures for the administration of the access system of industrial projects in the canal business district, especially the basic access conditions such as the requirements for scientific design registration, industrial layout, investment scale, investment intensity, output intensity, tax contribution, planning control index, environmental energy conservation and production safety. On the basis of source management, according to the entry system, environmental protection standards and economic contribution rate and other access systems, control the sold and unsold resource projects and strengthen comprehensive supervision.

3. The legal guarantee mechanism for the access of industrial projects in the canal business district, the Sub-center of Beijing, needs a multi-level guarantee system

To build a comprehensive system of the central top-level system design, strengthen legislation, law enforcement, judicial protection, play an important role in market allocation of resources and industry self-discipline. We should strictly introduce the entry management of the project, raise the threshold, fully consider the total factor productivity, and ensure that the real high-end project will be settled in the canal business district. Promote the opening of social services in the field of business services, encourage social capital venture capital and intellectual property services and other business services, and support social capital to participate in the transformation and restructuring of business service enterprises in this city through equity participation, merger and acquisition.

4. In the construction of the access mechanism for industrial projects in the canal business district, the Sub-center of Beijing, we should implement the concept of multiple co governance and focus on the relationship between the government and the market

In the government, industry associations, enterprises, social organizations and the public and other subjects to achieve common governance, comprehensive governance and

system governance. We should firmly grasp the strategic positioning of the capital, highlight the integration of high-end, service, agglomeration and low-carbon, adapt to the new normal of economic development, adhere to the focus on improving quality and efficiency, and optimize the development of service economy, knowledge economy and green economy.

IV. Experience and reference of legal regulation on the development of foreign urban CBD

A. Experience in the construction of urban central business system in the United States

The laws and regulations of CBD development in the United States are represented by New York City. New York's industrial restructuring is a successful model of industrial transformation. As the economic center of the United States, New York is also one of the world's financial, trade, cultural and information centers, and even one of the world's largest seaports and international political centers. New York's urban status is undoubtedly a very important financial and Trade Center. New York benefits from such a good economic center, because the relevant legal system of the United States is in place, and the training of high-quality labor force. The United States pays more attention to the economic development of new high technology. The United States attaches great importance to the development of service industry, especially the production and service industry serving various business exchanges, financial insurance, law, real estate, engineering design, scientific research and development activities, and the after-sales service industry serving education, health care and government policy departments. That's why CBD should learn from American experience.

In order to monitor the mistakes and risks that may damage the integrity of the securities market, enterprises need to have reasonable market access procedures. The "market access rules" stipulate that exchange or alternative trading systems, or the provision of these local brokers, must have full control over financial and regulatory risks, with the aim of preventing harm to the financial position of themselves or other market participants, so as to ensure the stability and integrity of the financial system and the securities market. The United States pays special attention to the improvement of the law. In the CBD, the United States is the representative of the family level, and improves the development of the CBD with the help of the law. This is what our country lacks at present. It also needs to be combined with the reality and discussed according to our country's specific national conditions. To learn from the advantages and experiences of the United States in the business district.

B. Experience in the system construction of German urban business district

In recent years, the development of German service industry reflects the characteristics of high-tech as the core and technological progress. Germany attaches great importance to the legal system and adopts a series of laws and regulations rather than a single one. All laws and regulations have made strict and detailed regulations on the operation and development of the CBD, so that there are laws to abide by, law enforcement must be strict, and violations must be punished. This is also what we need to learn at present. We need to improve our relevant laws and pay more attention to the development of the service industry. To build a central

business district, we need to build a perfect business district by combining high and new technology with many aspects and angles.

According to the current law of Germany, on the rules of access to the business district. For many years, the Social Democratic Party's platform has been calling for the improvement of the access rules of the business district, but it has been blocked due to the opposition of its conservative alliance partners, Christian Democratic Union and Christian Social Union. In the past, the radical left alliance camp has repeatedly claimed that Germany needs to be improved; later, the alliance stressed that there are many legal provisions in relevant fields, and there is no need to formulate special business district law. However, the SPD has different views. In an interview with Deutsche Telekom, burkhadleska, the party's internal affairs expert, said the current business district rules were "red tape monsters.". It can be seen that the laws promulgated must be applied to practice, for the benefit of the business district, and make a certain contribution to the building of the business district. Only in this way can we effectively promote the development of our country's business district, on this basis, can we promote the development of our country's relevant economy. We should learn from Germany's application in law.

C. Experience in system construction of Japanese urban business district

Facing the problems of urban construction, Japan chooses to start from Tokyo's international competitiveness [5], focusing on urban functions to build an intensive urban structure and an environment symbiotic City, enhancing the charm of urban character and promoting environment symbiosis, in order to complete the successful transformation of four regions. We will issue relevant laws and regulations to further improve the core functions, add new functions, avoid pendulum type areas, and increase interaction. In order to build Japan into a country with the most advantages in business services, our country needs to make use of Japan's reasonable arrangement and reasonable allocation of resources, so as to build China into the most powerful country [6]. The construction of CBD needs to be organized and arranged reasonably. If there is no order, there will be many unexpected problems.

Japan is building a business district, which is different from the United States and Germany. Japan pays attention to the overall construction and has relevant laws. It can be seen that western countries attach great importance to the authority of laws and regulations, as well as the guiding role of laws and regulations in the construction of business district, and can effectively regulate the healthy development of business district.

Japan has also established a business district access system and implemented strict access standards and identification systems. If businesses want to enter the platform of the business district, they must first go through the industrial and commercial registration procedures and go through the industrial and commercial registration procedures. They can apply for online products of trading companies through registration. Secondly, only after the completion of identity verification can businesses apply for online transactions and carry out trading activities. In addition, enterprises operating in the business district also need to accept third-

party certification. The credit investigation agency of Japan will conduct credit investigation on the businesses involved in e-commerce transactions and evaluate the business activities of the businesses according to the investigation results. In addition, the business platform operators in the business district are also obliged to entrust the logistics companies engaged in distribution to confirm the true identity of the buyer, in order to protect the interests of the businessmen from damage.

Japan has a complete set of laws and regulations for the traditional business district. As the overall level of commercial credit in Japan is high, the integrity and self-discipline of businesses are strong, and there are less trade disputes between the business district and consumers, which basically presents a virtuous circle in the business district transactions. Therefore, the Japanese government's intervention in the CBD is relatively small, and only when major events occur, the relevant government departments will intervene.

D. System construction experience of Singapore's urban business district

At the heart of Singapore's CBD is an orderly place with almost no voice to speak. There is no smoking, pushing or crowding in public. In terms of food, it is cheap and convenient, the streets are very clean and tidy, which gives people a fresh feeling, and Singapore has issued relevant laws and regulations to prohibit pollution of the surrounding environment, paying great attention to the environment. The reference for our country is that we need to attach great importance to the environment. It is not only to build a central business district for the purpose of building a central business district, but also to build a green Central Business District under the environment-oriented situation. Environment is one of the most concerned topics in recent years, so we should focus on environment when building CBD.

According to Singapore law, there is no special provision prohibiting foreign investors from carrying out construction projects in Singapore. However, under the building control ordinance, a person who does not hold a master contractor permit or a special contractor permit respectively shall not carry out general or special construction works in Singapore. In the case of Singapore construction companies, although there is no restriction on foreign ownership, it is a condition of a general contractor permit or a special contractor permit that the company applying for the permit must be incorporated in Singapore.

All companies registered, registered or operated in Singapore shall comply with the principles of the Contracts Act, the Companies Ordinance and its subsidiary regulations. In addition, the access to the business district must also comply with the code of conduct of the securities law and relevant regulations on the acquisition and merger of enterprises in Singapore, as well as the Listing Rules of relevant stock exchanges, such as the Singapore Exchange. Competition law should also be considered in mergers and acquisitions. The Act prohibits any act that is agreed or is actually intended to prevent, restrict or distort competition, constitutes abuse of market dominance in Singapore, and mergers and acquisitions result in or will result in a substantial reduction in competition in any market for goods or services.

In addition, Singapore pays attention not only to environmental protection, but also to the constraints and norms of laws and regulations on the business district. To be able to build Singapore's business district into a big city with law-abiding, beautiful and quality. It's very important for our country at this stage. It's in a new era. It's a very critical moment for the construction of economy and business district. We advocate the harmonious unity of man and nature, and attach importance to the real restriction and standardization of the construction of business district by law.

IV. Scientific path to optimize the industrial access system of canal business district, the Sub-center of Beijing

This topic mainly solves the problem of how to guarantee the coordinated development of the planning and construction objectives of the canal business district and sustainable health from the source of access through the innovation of ideas, the improvement of laws and policies, etc. On the basis of the catalogue of new industries in the urban area, we will study and formulate the catalogue of new industries, study and formulate the administrative measures for the access system of industrial projects in the canal business district, and promulgate the administrative system to achieve the best in terms of environmental pollution. What's more, we need to do a good job in urban management and supervision, strictly inspect the sold or not sold resource projects, implement management and control according to the access system of the settled business, environmental protection standards, economic contribution rate, etc., and comprehensively strengthen and improve the regulatory mechanism. Build the urban canal business district into a first-class institutionalized service industry [7]. There is an urgent need to study the scope of application, principles, rules, procedures and legal responsibilities of the industrial project access in the canal business district from the perspective of mechanism, and to explore the strategies for improving the access mechanism of the industrial project in the canal business district, the Sub-center of Beijing. With an area of 155 square kilometers of Beijing's urban Sub-center, the canal business district is the top priority. Comprehensively implement the latest concepts and highest standards proposed by the central and municipal Party committees, take the intersection of five rivers as the leader, high-end business as the main body, headquarters economy as the form, financial innovation, Internet industry, high-end services and other high-end industries as the focus, build a new super CBD with water city integration and blue-green interweaving, and connect with the international trade CBD 16 kilometers away, forming the east of Chang'an Street Two economic growth poles on the extension line.

A. Strengthen the top-level system design of industrial access in CBD at the national level

First of all, from the national level, the state needs to issue corresponding laws, regulations and rules to regulate development. Through the way of thinking and ruling by law, we should build a comprehensive system of the central top-level system design, strengthen legislation, law enforcement, judicial protection, and play an important role in market allocation of resources and industry self-discipline. It is necessary to strictly manage the project introduction and access, raise the threshold, fully consider the total factor productivity, and ensure that the truly high-end project is

located in the canal business district. We will promote the opening up of business services to social capital, encourage social capital to invest in business services such as venture capital and intellectual property services, and support social capital to participate in the transformation and restructuring of business service enterprises in this city by means of equity participation and M & A. To provide top-level system guarantee for the implementation of the industrial project access mechanism of Beijing Sub-center canal business district. If there is no system, the development of CBD will be disordered. The state also needs to implement the new development concept and integrate the development concept of the new era into the top-level system design of industrial access in the CBD. The state makes every effort to integrate industry and urban needs, interweave blue sky and green water, and integrate fresh and bright water resources with urban resources, so as to build China into an ecological and livable city. Under the strategy of promoting the protection and utilization of the Grand Canal cultural belt, we will ensure the construction of the canal business district from the perspective of source control, fully embody the basic requirements of "the most advanced concept, the highest standard and the best quality", and strive to be in line with the international first-class standards in improving urban functions, improving urban management level and strengthening public service matching.

At the national level, we will strengthen the top-level design of the CBD. At the national level, we need to set up relevant access systems according to the specific actual situation, strengthen supervision and supervision, prevent some risks, strengthen cooperation between the government and enterprises, promote business district cooperation, and attract social capital. According to the specific market access system, control the quality and quantity of enterprises' first cooperation, strong economic strength, strong sense of social responsibility, cross regional business layout and overall trader operation experience, enterprises with experience in cooperation with the government, establish projects in the intelligent business district, lead the system in the business district, explore the industrial development path, reduce vicious competition and realize social capital Source intensive optimization.

From the national level, it is very important to improve the access system of the Grand Canal Central Business District, which can effectively promote the rapid development of the central business district. To design the access mechanism of the canal business district, we need to implement the new development concept, especially put the construction of ecological civilization in a more prominent position, and strive to build an ecological livable city with "integration of industry and city, interweaving of blue and green, fresh and bright, integration of water and city, and intensive and compact multi group".

B. Improve the design of specific laws and policies for industrial access of Beijing urban business district

The industrial access system of Beijing Sub-center canal business district should be committed to improving the function undertaking system and improving the service guarantee ability for the central urban area. The construction of the industrial access system of the business district should be guided by the advanced concept to solve the problem of why to implement the new development

concept and the theory of urban Sub-center construction. Canal business district is the first and demonstration area of Beijing's Sub-center. Guided by the new development concept of innovation, coordination, green, opening and sharing, this paper optimizes the access concept of industrial projects and the adjustment mechanism of laws and policies in the canal business district, the Sub-center of Beijing. In the construction of the access mechanism for industrial projects in the canal business district, the Sub-center of Beijing City, we must implement the concepts of social standard, balance and coordination, source control and comprehensive system adjustment. Under the strategy of promoting the protection and utilization of the Grand Canal cultural belt, it is necessary to scientifically demonstrate the catalogue of industrial structural adjustment and guidance of the Grand Canal business district, in order to solve outstanding structural contradictions, effectively improve the quality and efficiency of industrial development of Beijing Sub Central Business District, promote the upgrading of industrial structure, and connect the functions of Beijing Sub central canal business district and Beijing central business district.

The specific legal and policy system of industrial access in Beijing urban business district needs to formulate and implement the positive list of industrial access in the canal business district and the positive list of industrial access in the canal business district; strictly control the scope, principles, conditions, review procedures, and legal responsibilities for the later stage inspection, supervision and management of the access. Strictly control the scope, that is to say, not all industries are allowed to enter. The principle of strict control should be based on environmental protection and fairness to actively promote economic development. The specific conditions meet the relevant laws and regulations issued by the state, the land conditions can meet the standards issued by the state, and the feasibility study report is provided. The review procedure is to provide feasibility study report, preliminary review, substantive review, project approval, project signing and other major aspects [8]. To a certain extent, it can ensure the rationality of entering the industry and the real orderly development of the business district, rather than any kind of industry, which will cause many unexpected problems. The post inspection of the project is also very important. Not only is it OK to enter the project, but also strict control, supervision, supervision and governance are needed, especially the legal responsibility. Whoever has a problem will bear his own responsibility. This paper discusses and solves the specific access system from the specific legal policy system level of Beijing Urban Business District, which can effectively build the central business district, which is also an effective standard of our country's legal policies.

C. Improve the implementation system of industrial project access of Beijing Sub-center canal business district

The planning of Beijing Urban Sub-center provides the planning framework for the industrial access rules of the canal business district. As for the implementation system of industrial project access in Beijing's Sub-center canal business district, this needs to be discussed from the aspects of implementation organization guarantee, implementation subject, implementation procedure, policy measures, rights and obligations, legal responsibilities, etc. The canal business district is located at the intersection of five rivers, the Sub-

center of the city. The most eye-catching planning scheme is the comprehensive development of regional underground space. Under the strategy of promoting the protection and utilization of Beijing Grand Canal cultural belt, in the construction of Beijing Sub-center canal business district, it is necessary to strictly manage the project introduction and access, improve the access threshold, fully consider the total factor productivity, ensure the implementation of real high-end projects, and build a high-end international Beijing Sub-center canal business district (CBD).

First of all, we need to improve the organizational guarantee mechanism. Without good organizational guarantee, the construction process of the canal business district will be blocked; with some sound organizational guarantee, the construction of Beijing Sub-center canal business district, especially the construction and implementation of the industrial access system, will be successfully implemented. Starting from the construction of organizational guarantee system, we should promote the canal business district, the Sub-center of Beijing, find the direction of financial development, strengthen the docking and cooperation with Xicheng Financial Street and Chaoyang CBD, undertake the industrial transfer, and promote the implementation of financial innovation business plate; actively explore and expand the use of foreign investment to attract competitive private enterprises and multinational companies Headquarters, to cultivate a growing headquarters with innovative vitality.

Secondly, improve the industrial access system of the canal business district, and scientifically design the scope, principles, conditions, review procedures (applicants provide feasibility study report, preliminary review, substantive review, project approval, project signing), post project inspection, supervision and management, legal responsibility and other system norms of the industrial project access of the canal business district, the Sub-center of Beijing city. On the basis of the catalogue of new industries in the urban area, research and formulate the catalogue of new industries, study and formulate the measures for the administration of the access system of industrial projects in the canal business district, implement the management and control of the resources projects that have been sold or not sold, and comprehensively strengthen and improve the supervision mechanism in accordance with the admission system of the settled business type, environmental protection standards, economic contribution rate, etc. From the industrial development and carrier to create the optimization and upgrading of industrial structure, and the design scheme must be scientific, forward-looking and feasible, not to say what kind of projects are put into it. Under the strategy of promoting the protection and utilization of the Grand Canal cultural belt, we should make good use of the tools of Beijing's Industrial Catalogue of prohibition and restriction, and introduce high-end business resources and projects into the canal business district. In particular, scientific design registration requirements, industrial layout requirements, investment scale requirements, investment intensity requirements, output intensity requirements, tax contribution requirements, planning control index requirements, environmental energy conservation requirements, production safety requirements and other basic access conditions. On the basis of source control, for the resource projects that have been sold or not,

the management and control shall be carried out in accordance with the access system such as the type of business settled in, environmental protection standards and economic contribution rate, and the supervision shall be strengthened in an all-round way.

Finally, we should optimize the industrial access procedures of the canal business district. We should deal with the dialectical relationship between the market allocation of resources and the role of the government. There should be strict implementation procedures for everything. We should do it step by step according to the procedures. We should not omit the steps by opportunism. We should strictly follow the procedures and regulations according to the different resident needs of different industries in combination with the development orientation of the business district. It is necessary to formulate relevant industry access assessment and annual assessment scoring standards, which is more conducive to the development of the business service area. The state should issue corresponding policies to support this development, make full use of the national model of developing high-end business area, and study and formulate the investment attraction mechanism and team building scheme of the canal business area, which are conducive to the construction of the city's central business area. To achieve the unity of rights and obligations, since it gives the implementer the power to exercise and enjoy the development of this business district, then at the same time, it is necessary to perform the obligations, and the rights and obligations are unified with each other. Finally, in terms of implementation, we need to clarify responsibilities and responsibilities. The main body is responsible for the problems. Strengthening the rigidity of the system is very conducive to improving the canal business district, the Sub-center of Beijing. From the specific project access of CBD to the specific system level to regulate the development of CBD, it can effectively solve the problems existing in the industry access level of CBD and effectively build the development of CBD.

D. Improve the judicial guarantee system for industrial access of canal business district, the Sub-center of Beijing

In order to strengthen the ecological environment and judicial protection of the central business district, optimize the working mechanism of environmental resources trial, we should run the corresponding laws and regulations in terms of access to the judicial security system, improve the level of environmental trial specialization, and actively build a centralized jurisdiction professional trial. Business district should focus on environmental protection, on the one hand, from the judicial system to ensure the development of business district. In the process of system operation, it is necessary to establish a docking mechanism among public security, procuratorial and court jurisdiction in different places, which is also for the better development of industrial and commercial areas. And we should also improve the coordination mechanism of judicial work, that is, "three mediation linkage" [9]: first, we should comprehensively improve the people's mediation work. Vigorously innovate and promote the ways and methods of people's mediation work, constantly strengthen the mediation of contradictions and disputes, strengthen the awareness of handling cases, improve the ability to handle cases, strictly handle cases, standardize the format and content of people's mediation

documents, and constantly improve the success rate of mediation and the implementation rate of agreements after mediation. Secondly, we should strengthen the work of administrative mediation. We should establish and improve administrative mediation organizations, clarify the competent organs of administrative mediation, strengthen the guidance of administrative mediation, and earnestly perform the functions of administrative mediation. We should, in accordance with the principles of voluntariness and legality, mediate and handle administrative disputes according to law and resolve administrative disputes in a timely manner. Finally, we will further promote judicial mediation. Comprehensively implement the principle of judicial mediation, adhere to the mediation for the cases that can be mediated, and the cases that need to be tried shall be tried according to law. The combination of mediation and trial will make the cases successfully resolved and realize the unity of legal effect and social effect. To achieve the goal of providing judicial guarantee for the construction of the access mechanism of industrial projects in the canal business district, the Sub-center of Beijing. From the perspective of the specific judicial security system, this is an effective guarantee for the development of the Grand Canal and the specific right to protect the specific industrial projects in the CBD. This can effectively promote the rapid development of business district, as well as the development of standardization.

E. Improve the market self-discipline and industry self-discipline mechanism of industrial access in Beijing Sub-center canal business district

In the process of implementing the concept of multiple co-governance, no matter which industry it is from, self-discipline needs to be done well. Self-discipline is conducive to the faster development of the industry and to a higher level. Market subjects should do their own things well, strictly do their own self-discipline, and can not develop the industry at will, otherwise, they will be subject to legal sanctions. We all know the importance of market order. Once it violates spontaneity and blindness, it will bring unnecessary troubles to the market. So in order to make the business district develop better, we should do a good job in the principles that the market should follow. First, we should do a good job in self-discipline. The same is true for the industry. Each industry has its own self-discipline rules. If the industry is allowed to develop at will, it will be not conducive to the development of the industry in the business district. Industry associations, intermediary organizations and autonomous organizations need to consciously implement the laws, regulations and relevant policies issued by the state, maximize the development of business service functions of Beijing Sub-center canal business district, and build a multi-dimensional and benign governance and operation mechanism of Sub-center canal business district. In a word, based on the existing rules and regulations, we will continue to improve the basic process of self-discipline investigation, consultation and reception process, industrial dispute mediation process, legal consultant work process, legal affairs assistance process and other basic systems. To supervise the real estate service process of the real estate service enterprises, pay attention to the integrity and self-discipline management of the industry, increase the illegal cost of the enterprise, and promote the healthy development of the industry. From the perspective of self-discipline, market access self-discipline is an important mechanism for

the industry to be cautious. In addition to the above specific countermeasures, the final one is the market access self-discipline of the industrial projects themselves, which is an effective solution to the specific development of the industrial projects in the CBD.

To sum up, the business service function of Beijing Sub-center canal business district is the core, and at the same time, it should undertake the functions of Beijing Central Business District and Beijing Tianjin Hebei collaborative development demonstration function; the functional structure should be reasonable, and can guarantee the realization of CBD "24-hour vitality". In the construction of the access mechanism for industrial projects in the canal business district, the Sub-center of Beijing, we should implement the concept of multiple co governance, and focus on the relationship between the government and the market. We should realize the coordinated governance, comprehensive governance and systematic governance among the government, industry association, enterprise subject, social organization, social public and other subjects. Firmly grasp the strategic positioning of the capital city, highlight the high-end, service-oriented, agglomeration, integration and low-carbon, adapt to the new normal of leading economic development, adhere to the improvement of quality and efficiency as the center, and optimize the development of service economy, knowledge economy and green economy. The construction of Beijing Sub-center should integrate Beijing, Tianjin and Hebei's national strategy, one belt strategy and the Grande Canale cultural strategy, and strengthen the integration advantage of [10]. To promote sustainable development, the canal business district, the Sub-center of Beijing, must rely on industrial support and capital drive. Therefore, it is necessary to integrate the advantages of industrial capital, media and talent intelligence of Beijing, Tianjin and Hebei, make good use of the integration advantages of national professional teams and local cultural experts, plan the industrial strategy of the canal business district, the Sub-center of Beijing, attract social capital, build the green ecological and cultural tourism economic belt of the Grand Canal, promote the equalization of advertising services, and promote the cultural services along the river Equalization, improve the quality of life and quality of life of people along the river, and improve the happiness index and people's well-being. From the specific level of the country to strengthen the top-level access system design, from the perspective of the government to improve the legal policy system design, from the industrial project itself, from the judicial system of industrial access, the market industry self-discipline, industry self-discipline. The construction of canal business district, the Sub-center of Beijing City, needs further study,

and there are more issues worthy of attention. Based on the positioning of the city's Sub-center, focusing on the high-end service industry, making good use of the policy advantages of Beijing's service industry to expand the comprehensive pilot of opening up and upgrade again, and further deepening and refining the functional positioning and industrial layout of the canal business district. On the basis of rational planning of land use function, realize rational and sustainable development of functional structure of business office, business service, public facilities and residence.

Reference

- [1] Wang Chengrong, Han Ningchun, Kang Jian. Thinking about the development of new CBD in Tongzhou District, the Sub-center of Beijing City [J]. Business era, 2014, (30): 135-138.
- [2] yuan Songhua. Beijing's urban Sub-center construction promotes Beijing, Tianjin and Hebei to become the third pole of China's economy [J]. China development observation, 2016 (12): 16-18.
- [3] Zheng Ruifang. International comparison and Enlightenment on the construction of Tongzhou City Sub-center in Beijing [J]. China Statistics, 2017, (03): 7-9.
- [4] Liangpeng Zhu, Shuming Jiang, Shijie Xu, Jinfeng Miao. The Morden City Central Business District Evolution Simulation. Chapter 87.
- [5] Li Wei, Zhu Jiaguang. The formation of multi center city structure: a case study of Tokyo [J]. Beijing Planning and construction, 2003, (06): 23-25.
- [6] Wu Lingjie, Qu Tao. Comparison of urban Sub-center development modes between China and Japan [J]. China's famous cities, 2011, (12): 43-47.
- [7] Hu Xin, Zhao Ying. Research on the positioning of urban Sub-center business district [J]. Research on urban development, 2003, (06): 35-40.
- [8] Jiang sangeng, Wang Zhen. Analysis on the innovation of the management mode of the central business district [J]. Journal of Capital University of economics and trade, 2015, (03): 83-90.
- [9] Luo Yongtai, Zhang jinjuan. Research on the development of China's central business district [J]. Urban development research, 2004, (03): 28-32.
- [10] Yang Wuyang, Xie Dongxiao. Current situation and prediction of central business district in Beijing [J]. Urban issues, 1992, (06): 16-19